

“Communicate, argue, share your ideas”: Values in talking and values in silence

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Many mathematics curricula emphasise the importance of communication in mathematics classrooms, supported by an extensive body of research. In much of the world, this emphasis promotes specific communicational practices as necessary or desirable in order to support mathematical meaning-making and effective learning of mathematics. In this paper, we seek to question the implied universality of this approach: in Arendt’s terms, we seek to judge, in order to provoke questioning and rethinking. Our examination draws on the idea of social norms. We consider what happens when children in mathematics classrooms orient to different norms from those assumed to be beneficial for learning mathematics and how could the epistemological effect of such orientation be conceptualised.

Communication has come to occupy an important place in efforts to develop forms of teaching and learning mathematics that result in conceptual understanding, rather than an exclusive focus on procedural fluency. This emphasis is apparent in curriculum documents in many parts of the world. The recommendations or requirements of such documents often reflect what is known as ‘reform’ mathematics approaches, in which students are expected to play an active part in mathematics classroom activity, through posing and solving problems, often in small groups, as well as participating in whole-class interaction. Among other practices, students are expected to pose questions to their peers and respond to such questions, as well as explain their thinking to the class. These curricular guidelines are supported, often explicitly, by much research in mathematics education (e.g., Cobb & Bauersfeld, 1995).

While such work is valuable, and the goal of conceptual understanding is significant, our work with students from diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds leads us to trouble its perhaps unintended and implied universality. In our experiences in mathematics classrooms with children from Indigenous backgrounds or immigrant backgrounds we have come to wonder if the reform approach to mathematics classroom interaction unjustifiably assumes or even imposes supposedly universal values. We also wonder and attempt to judge what the impact of these unstated assumptions might be.

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Who is to judge?

In her book of *Responsibility and Judgement*, Arendt (2003) analyzed the relation among thinking (and not thinking), responsibility, and the capacity for developing of moral judgement. As the foundation for thoughts and analysis, she uses events in the history (such as human interactions in the World War II) to relate judgment with human dignity. She explains human dignity could be claimed neither through valorising history nor through denying history's significance, but rather through judging. She views judging as an activity that recognises history but goes even further to deny the histories right to be the ultimate judge. That is, being historically "there", doesn't mean that it should be there! Arendt's view of judgment is particularly important because in different curricula, the endorsement of communication in mathematics classes is there, but the effects of is belonging for students with different epistemological roots (Abtahi, 2019) is not questioned. Here, we took the liberty to judge and we extend the invitation to others. While judging, Arendt explains, we are able to look back at, reflect upon, and begin to make sense of the affairs that are related to our communities, and to form individual standpoints. The more people's take stands and the more standpoints being present [...] while we are ponder a given issue, "the better I [we] can imagine how I [we] would feel and think if I [we] were in their place, the stronger will be our capacity for representative thinking" (Arendt, 1993, p. 241).

Given how communication is endorsed in different curricula and given how values are therefore perpetuated or ignored, we seek to judge the significance of specific forms of communication as crucial foundations of the learning and teaching of mathematics. Communication is, of course, a part of human social life. So the issue is not whether there should be communication in mathematics classrooms (or in the curriculum) but how it is presented and practiced? And who decides? And how should we, as mathematics educators, judge its normalisation?

The origins of reform approaches: Sociomathematical norms

Ways of interacting in small groups, in large groups, among children or between children and adults vary in different societies or among different groups within societies. Heath's (1983) classic work on literacies, for example, showed clearly that children growing up in middle class White households, working class Black households and working class White households, in southern USA, all developed different repertoires of literacy practices, including different ways of talking and interacting around texts. For example, the uses of stories and ways of telling them varied, as did ways of interacting around a recently received letter.

The significance of Heath's study for education was that the repertoires of the middle class White children in her study aligned most closely with literacy practices in school. Those of the working class children did not align and were often seen as deficient. The example of Heath's work could be interpreted as an advantage of middle class White children, for whom

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parents have time and resources to educate them in line with what they, themselves, have learnt as children – hence reproducing the same repertoires. Judging more closely, we see that the norms of literacy practices in school are also aligned with the reproduction of middle class White social norms. For children from the other two backgrounds, there was a misalignment. Such misalignments may not only be due to class: children of many cultural backgrounds whose parents have time and resources to help their children will develop different repertoires of literacy practices, would therefore experience a misalignment of norms and hence be perceived as having some kind of deficit. A study by Street, Baker and Tomlin (2005) focused on numeracy practices showed exactly this.

In a now classic paper, Yackel and Cobb (1996) proposed a social perspective on mathematics classroom interaction. This approach drew on social constructivism, social interactionism and ethnomethodological principles. This last influence was apparent in Yackel and Cobb’s adoption of the idea of norms. They proposed two kinds of norm that were of significance in mathematics classrooms: social norms, and sociomathematical norms. It is important to note that from an ethnomethodological perspective, as Yackel and Cobb note, norms are not pre-ordained sets of rules governing human interaction. There is a reflexive relationship between behaviour and norms, through which interaction reflects prevailing norms, but also contributes to their interpretation, so that over time, norms will change. Here is how Yackel and Cobb explain social and sociomathematical norms:

Our prior research has included analyzing the process by which teachers initiate and guide the development of social norms that sustain classroom microcultures characterized by explanation, justification, and argumentation. Norms of this type are, however, general classroom social norms that apply to any subject matter area and are not unique to mathematics. For example, ideally students should challenge others’ thinking and justify their own interpretations in science or literature classes as well as in mathematics. In this paper we extend our previous work on general classroom norms by focusing on normative aspects of mathematics discussions specific to students’ mathematical activity. To clarify this distinction, we will speak of *sociomathematical* norms rather than social norms. For example, normative understandings of what counts as mathematically different, mathematically sophisticated, mathematically efficient, and mathematically elegant in a classroom are sociomathematical norms. Similarly, what counts as an acceptable mathematical explanation and justification is a sociomathematical norm. (pp. 460–461)

Yackel and Cobb acknowledge that social and sociomathematical norms will vary in different classrooms. Nevertheless, their paper clearly favours particular norms that they see as productive of mathematical meaning-making and learning, such as their focus on explanation, justification and argumentation. The paper appears to assume that certain practices are ‘normal’ in classrooms and that the teacher plays a strong socializing role in guiding the development of desirable norms. These ideas can be seen in many mathematics curriculum documents. To illustrate this point, in the next section we look at two mathematics curricula with which we are familiar.

Two mathematics curricula

Theories of social reproduction, such as those articulated by Bourdieu and Passeron (1977) and by Bernstein (1975, 1996), explain the fact that curricula play roles in reproducing social qualities and values by constructing and presenting particular types of knowledge as legitimate. Apple (1979) emphasises the idea that the ideologically-based contents of curricula legitimate some kinds of values and make them appear natural and consistent with common sense. That is, in mathematics curricula, some actions and interactions are valued and legitimised as norms and natural. For example, in the new Norwegian mathematics curriculum, “fagfornyelsen” (Kunnskapsdepartementet, 2020), the broad concept of competence is translated into basic communication skills (to speak, to read, to write, to count and digital skills). All these competencies are also strongly linked to basic communication skills. There is a specific emphasis on dialogue and participation (Skolforskningsinstituttet, 2018). The curriculum includes the following:

Dialogue is crucial in social learning, and the school must teach the value and importance of a listening dialogue to deal with opposition. When interacting with their pupils, the teachers must promote communication and collaboration that will give the pupils the confidence and courage to express their own opinions and to point out issues on the behalf of others. To learn to listen to others and also argue for one’s own views will give the pupils the platform for dealing with disagreements and conflicts, and for seeking solutions together. Everyone must learn to cooperate, function together with others and develop the ability to participate and take responsibility. The pupils and their homes are also responsible for contributing to a good environment and sense of belonging. Just as each pupil contributes to the environment in school, so will this environment contribute to the individual’s well-being, development and learning. (Ministry of Education of Norway, 2020)

The newly revised Ontario Mathematics Curriculum (OMC) for elementary schools also gives explicit attention to communication, and highlights “understanding local and global perspectives and societal and cultural contexts, and using a variety of media appropriately, responsibly, safely”. The curriculum documents include the following:

Communication is an essential process in learning mathematics. Students communicate for various purposes and for different audiences, such as the teacher, a peer, a group of students, the whole class, a community member, or their family. They may use oral, visual, written, or gestural communication. Communication also involves active and respectful listening. Teachers provide differentiated opportunities for all students to acquire the language of mathematics, developing their communication skills, which include expressing, understanding, and using appropriate mathematical terminology, symbols, conventions, and models.

For example, teachers can ask students to:

1. share and clarify their ideas, understandings, and solutions;
2. create and defend mathematical arguments;
3. provide meaningful descriptive feedback to peers; and
4. pose and ask relevant questions.

Effective classroom communication requires a supportive, safe, and respectful environment in which all members of the class feel comfortable and valued when they speak and when they question, react to, and elaborate on the statements of their peers and the teacher. (Ontario Ministry of Education, 2020)

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These extracts raise many questions for us. What are the assumptions about communication (talking, interacting, social participation, social roles, etc.) revealed by these guidelines? One assumption seems to be that children should talk about their ideas. “Defending mathematical arguments” or “pointing out issues” might assume situations where someone has to convince others that they are right or criticise the ideas of classmates. Asking questions, active participation and communication seem to be idealised as signatures of a successful and engaging mathematics classroom.

We depart from Yackel and Cobb view of social norms and sociomathematical norms in our examination of the endorsement of communication in the mathematics classrooms, as highlighted in Norway (2020) and Ontario (2020) Mathematics Curricula. As mentioned by Yackel and Cobb, interaction reflects dominant norms, but at the same time, interactions contribute to the interpretation of the norms, making the norms change over time. We agree with such a view that norms and sociomathematical norms are reflexively produced and are changed in interactions and over time. We do not wish to be concerned with the soundness of this position but with what it means to a knower. Knowers are ones who grew up and were socialised into various norms (and sociomathematical norms) different from presented by the dominant classroom culture and of mathematics itself. We challenge Yackel and Cobb’s perspective to examine epistemological assumptions such as: How do children come to know these norms? How are the epistemological effects of these norms conceptualised? And how do the norms of a group of people interact with and cause harm to the norms of another group of people? We think about these questions with a confined focus on the endorsement of communication. We attempt to judge the given value to ‘communication’ in mathematics classrooms. We judge to form a standpoint, and in the collection of many other standpoints, to contribute to a more just teaching and learning of mathematics.

These are mandates of the curricula, which by legitimising certain types of knowledge, and certain ways of acquiring that knowledge reproduce certain social qualities and values. Curricula, of course, are themselves embedded in and reflect particular societal norms and assumptions. Hence our fundamental questions become: how should cultural and, more importantly, epistemological sensitivity be conceptualised? And who is responsible to judge?

Speech, silence and communication in mathematics classrooms

Speech is silver and silence is gold – says a Filipino saying. Stay silent and reflect so that your thoughts become selected and strong speeches (or something like it) – says a Persian saying. One of the central instructions to many children worldwide is to practice quietness, listen, and speak only if one knows the full meaning of what one says.

Don’t talk too often ... Don’t talk too long ... Don’t talk about those matters you know nothing about. Johnston (1990) explains that “Were a person to restrict his discourse, and measure his speech, and govern his talk by what he knew, he would earn the trust and respect of his [or her] listeners ... people would want to hear the speaker again and by so doing would bestow upon the speaker the opportunity to speak, for ultimately it is the people who confer the right of speech by their audience.” (p. 210). For many cultures, words are not

objects to be wasted. They represent the accumulated knowledge, cultural values, the vision of entire peoples. Armstrong, a Cree philosopher, explains:

It is said that you cannot call your words back once they are uttered, and so you are responsible for all which results from your words. It is said that, for those reasons, it is best to prepare very seriously and carefully to make public contributions. (1999, p. 90)

Not once but many times both in Norway (2020) and in Ontario (2020), Mathematics Curricula, communication is encouraged for multiple reasons. For example, communication is valued as it gives “the pupils the confidence and courage to express their own opinions” (Ministry of Education of Norway, 2020). Pupils are inspired to “argue for one’s own views” to create a “platform for dealing with disagreements and conflicts and seeking solutions together” (Ministry of Education of Norway, 2020). Similarly, in OMC, communication is highlighted as “an essential process in learning mathematics”. In OMC, developing communication skills is directly related to “expressing” and “understanding mathematical terminology, symbols, conventions, and models” (OMC).

Following the line of arguments in Norway (2020) and in Ontario (2020) Mathematics Curricula, in emphasis on the benefit of having communications and expression of an idea in the mathematics classroom, specifically to better understand mathematics, raised concerns for us. Could such a view of communication imply that silence is the opposite of knowing? That a student who is silent and does not “express” or “argue” her position (because she has learnt the fundamental values of being silence) now is considered as not understanding “mathematical terminology, symbols, conventions, and models”? This consideration - of not understanding - is precisely the point in which epistemological sensitivity is vital. Without such sensitivity to the ways in which students with different social and sociomathematical norm become to be normalised in the dominant norms (i.e. those of the curricula), who thrives, who survives and who get disappeared? If according to Norway (2020) competence translates into basic communication then silence becomes a marginalised capacity, showing lack of competency.

Interpreting students’ knowing and participation

The following extract is from an interview conducted in 2010 with a Canadian elementary school teacher. It was conducted at the end of the school year, in which she had taught a class composed for most of the year of Cree children (see Barwell, 2020, for information about the study). In this extract, she is reflecting on some of the children’s participation.

I would say [Curtis] is the strongest one in the whole class with regards to math skills and confidence (.) he is willing to take risks and doesn’t care if he is wrong as he will learn from it very quickly (.)
um the other kids [...] um they are a lot less likely to take those risks (.) much more hesitant for a number of reasons I would say (.) one (.) they are not at school regularly (.) they are not here to hear everything like a concept or a lesson half way through and they have no idea what has been taught before or what is coming so (.) they have gaps of learning (.) they’re not they’re

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unsure and they just don't really want to participate (.) they don't see the importance in what they are doing (.)

then you have someone kind of in the middle like Kevin (.) who wants to participate who wants to ask questions who wants to do well and try and things like that (.) but is so unsure (.) his skills like (.) he is so unsure of himself that he doesn't want to risk being embarrassed or things like that sometimes (.) sometimes he is okay but sometimes I know he is nervous about being wrong (.) and I think that is one of the biggest things that we have overcome.

The teacher's observations reflect the kinds of mathematics classroom norms we have been discussing. She refers positively to risk-taking, participating and asking questions. She refers to hesitancy, or being unsure as more problematic. But what if her interpretations, based on the implicitly adopted and reproduced norms, as found in many curriculum documents, are a misreading of behaviours of children from a cultural background quite different from her own and largely unfamiliar to her?

Abtahi (2019) warns us about the danger of an over-emphasis on cultural difference and neglecting the elements underlying the cultural differences, which are differences in ways of becoming to know, in mathematics classrooms. Similarly, for us, what is worrisome is beyond the cultural differences or even the diversity of social norms and sociomathematical norms. Instead, we are concerned with the epistemological differences and particularly are perturbed by the effect that such differences play in Curtis' or Kevin's mathematics learning. For example, in the above quote, the possibility of students' orientation to silence and humility as a cultural norm is ignored. This legitimate form of participation leads to the interpretation of Kevin's action as hesitancy, nervousness or a lack of willingness to take risks, leading to a (possibly harmful) epistemological assumption that Kevin “is someone kind of in the middle” and his sorts of behaviour “is one of the biggest things that we have overcome”.

We are not attempting to force an interpretation on the data here. Instead, in our judgment of the content of the curriculum, concerning the significance of communication and the endorsement of silence in different cultures, we are highlighting possibilities of epistemological diversities that, if ignored, could be harmful. We note also that teachers judge their students' participation in mathematics – it can be difficult not to – and that sometimes these judgements will be harmful to the students.

Discussion

In many parts of the world's mathematical curricula, communicational practices are desirable to support better understanding and learning of mathematics. In many parts of the world, silence is desirable to support deeper understanding and reflection on any phenomena. Knowing the value of silence in many cultures around the world, knowing that human movement from places to places and knowing the significance of communication in mathematics classrooms, in this paper, we set out to judge the relationships among these three assumptions and highlighted possible epistemological implications. We examined the content of Canada (2020) and Norway (2020) mathematics curricula to better understand

their framing of the significance of communication in mathematics classrooms. We noticed not only that argumentation, expression and communication are highly endorsed in both curricula, but also that the lack of such abilities is viewed as not understanding mathematical ideas. Following Arendt's view on judgment, we judged how the emphasis on communication, contradicts with social and sociomathematical norms of some communities leading to not just cultural but epistemological ignorance. We finish this paper with an open question of how epistemological mindfulness could promote more just mathematics learning and teaching and how epistemological mindfulness could look to different teachers?

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